

Supplementary Table 1A. Effect of time on OAT1 transport kinetics

Incubation Time	J_{max}	K_m	CL_{int}
	<i>(pmol · min⁻¹ · 10⁶ cells⁻¹)</i>	<i>(μM)</i>	<i>(μl · min⁻¹ · 10⁶ cells⁻¹)</i>
15 sec	24.9 ± 9	4.4 ± 0.6	5.5 ± 1.6
1 min	21.3 ± 7.7	4.4 ± 0.5	4.8 ± 1.6
5 min	16 ± 5.1	6.7 ± 0.7	2.4 ± 0.7
10 min	9.1 ± 1.7	7 ± 0.6	1.4 ± 0.4
30 min	6.7 ± 4.9	5.3 ± 0.4	1.2 ± 0.07
45 min	3.9 ± 2.7	6.8 ± 0.3	0.5 ± 0.3

Data are mean ± SEM of four experiments. Significant differences in kinetic parameters determined at different time points (15 sec to 45 min) were determined by One-Way ANOVA. There was a significant effect of time on all three kinetic parameters: J_{max} ($P < 0.05$), K_m ($P < 0.01$), and CL_{int} ($P < 0.01$).

Supplementary Table 1B. Effect of time on OAT1 inhibition

Inhibitor	IC₅₀, μM		Fold change
	(15 sec)	(10 min)	
Omeprazole	9.7 ± 0.8	9.2 ± 0.8	1.1
Furosemide	19.6 ± 3	15.1 ± 2.2	1.3
Indomethacin	5.9 ± 0.5	12.7 ± 1.4**	2.2
Probenecid	9.3 ± 1.3	5.1 ± 0.6*	1.8
Telmisartan	0.4 ± 0.07	0.06 ± 0.02**	6.7

Data are mean ± SEM of four experiments. * $P < 0.05$, ** $P < 0.001$, indicates significant differences in IC₅₀ values between 15 sec and 10 min, unpaired Student's *t* test.